

1 **Whole genome sequence *Ensifer* sp. VA4 a nitrogen fixing bacterium associated with**
2 ***Vigna anguiculata* L. walp. from Timimoun (Algeria)**

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22 **Abstract**

23 This study reports the whole-genome sequence (WGS) of an endophytic bacterial strain isolated
24 from efficient root nodules of *Vigna unguiculata* collected from Ksar Ben Aissa (Tmimoun,
25 Algeria). The strain, identified as *Ensifer* sp., exhibits nitrogen-fixing activity and associates
26 with the host plant in a symbiotic manner, contributing to nitrogen nutrition in low-fertility
27 soils. Whole-genome sequencing will provide valuable insights into the genetic basis of
28 nodule-associated endophytic behaviour and nitrogen fixation, facilitating the development and
29 application of this strain in sustainable agriculture in desert environments.

30 **Key words:** *Vigna unguiculata*, nodules, WGS, Desert, *Ensifer*, nitrogen fixation

31 **Introduction**

32 Leguminous plants play a central role in soil fertility and sustainable agriculture due to their
33 unique ability to acquire atmospheric nitrogen through symbiotic associations with
34 nodule-forming bacteria such as *Rhizobium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, and *Ensifer* (Kearsley et al.,
35 2024; Srivastava et al., 2025). These microorganisms infect the roots of legumes, induce the
36 formation of specialized structures called root nodules, and within these nodules carry out
37 biological nitrogen fixation (BNF), converting molecular nitrogen (N₂) into ammonia (NH₃),
38 which is then assimilated by the host plant (Chiurazzi et al., 2025). This process significantly
39 reduces the dependence on synthetic nitrogen fertilizers, mitigating environmental impacts such
40 as nitrate leaching and greenhouse gas emissions (Bhatt et al., 2025).

41 The genus *Ensifer* (formerly included within *Sinorhizobium*) comprises a group of
42 α -proteobacteria best known for their ability to form nitrogen-fixing root nodules on a wide
43 range of leguminous plants, including crops such as *Vigna*
44 *unguiculata* (cowpea), *Medicago*, *Trifolium*, and *Cicer* species (Fagorzi et al., 2020). Within
45 these nodules, *Ensifer* strains differentiate into bacteroids that reduce atmospheric nitrogen (N₂)

46 into ammonia, a form readily assimilated by the host plant, thereby improving nitrogen nutrition
47 without the need for synthetic fertilizers (Pacheco et al., 2023). This symbiotic nitrogen fixation
48 not only boosts legume productivity but also enriches the soil with biologically fixed nitrogen,
49 benefiting subsequent crops in rotation systems and contributing to more sustainable
50 agricultural practices (Qiao et al., 2024).

51 In addition to their well-defined symbiotic role, *Ensifer* strains often exhibit traits that extend
52 beyond nodule formation. Many isolates possess plant growth-promoting abilities such as
53 indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) production, phosphate solubilization, siderophore secretion, and
54 tolerance to abiotic stresses including salinity, drought, and heavy metals (Bhatt et al., 2026).
55 These features enable *Ensifer* to persist in diverse soils and to support host plants under
56 suboptimal or marginal agricultural conditions (Cambeis et al., 2025).

57 Given these capacities, efficient symbiotic nitrogen fixation and broad plant growth-promoting
58 functions, *Ensifer* represents a highly promising candidate for the development of targeted
59 microbial inoculants in agriculture. Integrating *Ensifer* strains into microbial consortia that also
60 include free-living diazotrophs and other beneficial rhizobacteria offers the potential to enhance
61 nitrogen availability throughout the cropping season, stabilize yields under stress, and reduce
62 reliance on chemical fertilizers. The present study focuses on an *Ensifer* sp. strain isolated from
63 root nodules of *Vigna unguiculata*, aiming to characterize its genome, nitrogen fixation-related
64 genes, and plant growth-promoting traits, with a view to its potential application in sustainable
65 legume-based cropping systems.

66 **Material and Methods**

67 **1. Sample collection and isolation**

68 Root nodules of *Vigna unguiculata* were collected from plants growing at an agricultural parcel
69 Ksar Ben Aissa (Timimoun), Algeria. Nodules were carefully detached from the root system,

70 placed in sterile polyethylene bags, and transported to the laboratory in an icebox. Samples
71 were processed within 24 h of collection and the bacterium was isolated from surface-sterilized
72 nodules using the direct nodule isolation method. An individual nodule was opened with a
73 sterile scalpel and using a toothpick, the bacterium was streaked directly onto yeast extract–
74 mannitol (YEM) medium. After incubation, at $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 7 days, single colonies were selected
75 and further purified and named VA4.

76 **3. Whole-genome sequencing of bacteria**

77 The genomic DNA of strain VA4 was obtained by MicrobesNG. The concentration of DNA
78 was quantified using the Quant iT dsDNA HS kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and libraries were
79 constructed employing the Nextera XT kit (Illumina) on a Hamilton Microlab STAR system.
80 Sequencing was conducted on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) utilising
81 a 250 bp paired-end technique. Reads underwent adapter trimming utilising Trimmomatic v0.30
82 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality threshold of Q15. De novo assembly was
83 conducted with SPAdes v3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012), and contigs were annotated with Prokka
84 v1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

85 **Results**

86 **Genomic features**

87 The sequence data is available from NCBI/GenBank under the BioProject: [PRJNA1429578](#).

88 The whole genome sequencing of the strain VA4 (BioSample SAMN56136948) was
89 conducted. The sequence reads were assembled using QUAST, yielding 44 contigs (≥ 1000 bp).
90 The largest contig measured 632,243 base pairs (bp), while the total genome assembly length
91 for strain VA4 was 6,335,590 bp. The genomic G + C content of strain VA4 was determined to
92 be 62.39%, with a mean coverage of $26.31\times$ and an *N50* of 358,937 bp. The total number of

93 genes, including 5,994 protein-coding genes (CDS), 54 tRNA genes, and 8 rRNA genes, is
94 presented in **Table 1**.

95 **Data availability**

96 The raw reads are available under GenBank accession SRR38007193, and the genome
97 assembly under JBVQPO000000000.1. Based on Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) analysis
98 and current taxonomic classification, the genome sequence of strain VA4 will be further
99 characterized for species assignment within the *Ensifer* genus.

100 **Statement on continuing work**

101 The datasets are being shared prior to formal publication and should be considered preliminary.
102 We encourage and welcome feedback from the scientific community. Please get in touch with
103 **Nadjette Djemouai** (djemouai.nadjette@univ-ghardaia.dz) for more information.

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105 **Table 1.** Summary statistics for the genomes studied

Bacterial strain	Biosample	Number of contigs (>=1000 bp)	Largest contig	Total length	GC (%)	Mean coverage	N50	CDS	tRNA	rRNA	GenBank accession (Assembly)	GenBank accession (reads)
VA4	SAMN56136948	44	632,243	6,335,590	62.39	26.31	358,937	5,994	54	8	JBVQPO000000000.1	SRR38007193

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